

Research article

Key areas for the conservation of endangered reptile species in the Kresna Gorge, south-western Bulgaria

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Abstract: Kresna Gorge and the broader Struma River Valley in south-western Bulgaria host high species diversity, including species of conservation importance and locally restricted distribution. Precise published data on amphibian and reptile distributions, however, are limited and incomplete. Here we summarised 2834 precise distribution records from the herpetofauna in the region, focusing on four key species of conservation importance: *Testudo graeca*, *T. hermanni*, *Elaphe quatuorlineata* and *Za-*

menis situla. We identified three areas of importance for the key species within the study area, confirming the significance of Kresna Gorge. The key species were mostly found at lower elevations, near the major road E79; automotive traffic presents a major threat to the populations.

Keywords: Amphibia, conservation, distribution, mapping, Reptilia, road mortality

Introduction

Kresna Gorge along Struma River is an area important for the Bulgarian and European herpetofauna, due to its high species richness, including taxa with limited distribution (Petrov & Beshkov, 2001; Stojanov et al., 2011). It is situated in south-western Bulgaria, between the eastern slopes of Maleshevska Mts and the western slopes of Pirin Mts. Within the gorge, Continental and Mediterranean climates interact, forming its specific climate and contributing to its species diversity. For instance, the northern end of the gorge marks the northern limit of the distribution of three Mediterranean species: *Lacerta trilineata* Bedriaga, 1886, *Elaphe quatuorlineata* (Bonnaterre, 1790), and *Zamenis situla* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Petrov & Beshkov, 2001; Naumov & Tomović, 2007; Stojanov et al., 2011; Beschkov, 2015c, d). Due to its conservation importance as a natural bio-corridor for plant and animal species, it was included in the NATURA 2000 network as part of “BG0000366 Kresna - Ilindentsi” Special Area of Conservation (SAC). Ten amphibian and 21 reptile species inhabit Kresna Gorge (Petrov & Beshkov, 2001), all protected by national and/or international legislation (Biological Diversity Act of Bulgaria, Council Directive 92/43/EEC, and the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats, Bern). Two amphibian (*Triturus ivanbureschi* Arntzen & Wielstra, 2013 and *Bombina variegata* (Linnaeus, 1758)) and five reptile species (*Emys orbicularis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Testudo hermanni* Gmelin, 1789, *Testudo graeca* Linnaeus, 1758, *Elaphe quatuorlineata* (Bonnaterre, 1790), and *Zamenis situla* (Linnaeus, 1758)) are also included in Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC. Two of those seven species are with very limited distribution in Bulgaria. *Zamenis situla* is distributed only along the southern Black Sea Coast and along Struma River Valley, while *E. quatuorlineata* is distributed only along Struma River Valley. For both species, Kresna Gorge marks a local northern boundary of their ranges (Naumov & To-

mović, 2007; Stojanov et al., 2011; Beschkov, 2015c, d). Even though the gorge is a very popular area for both herpetological studies and for wildlife photography, published data on the distribution of the herpetofauna, especially on species of conservation importance (e.g. such as those from Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC) are scarce. Most publications provide limited locality data for the species of conservation importance in the Kresna Gorge and the surroundings: they are either purely faunistic (e.g. Buresh & Zonkow, 1933, 1934, 1941, 1942; Beshkov, 1961; Beškov & Beron, 1964; Petrov & Beshkov, 2001), or focus on their ecology, biology or morphology (Beshkov, 1974, 1978; Beshkov & Nankinov, 1979; Beshkov & Gerasimov, 1980; Beshkov & Dushkov, 1981; Stojanov, 2000; Naumov et al., 2020; Mitrevichin et al., 2023a). On the other hand, publications with distribution data often utilise small resolution maps, e.g. 10×10 km UTM squares (Naumov & Tomović, 2007; Mollov et al., 2013a; Beschkov, 2015a, b, c, d; Kornilev et al., 2017), or maps without coordinates (Mitrevichin et al., 2023b, c). Few studies provide limited specific distribution records for some species (Grozdanov et al., 2016; Dyugmedzhiev et al., 2019).

Roads, especially those with heavy traffic, can effectively serve as barriers for reptile movements and migration, and lead to significant mortality (Ashley & Robinson, 1996; Smith & Dodd, 2003; Meek, 2009). A specific local example is the major two-lane international road E79 (Hungary–Romania–Bulgaria–Greece) that passes through Kresna Gorge. Numerous individuals of multiple species are killed on the road each year (Petrov et al., 2006; authors’ personal observations). Its intensive vehicular traffic has increased exponentially in the past decades, especially as a result of the integration of Bulgaria into the EU in 2006. Since then, the government of Bulgaria has periodically pushed for the realisation of a strategic infrastructural project, aiming to incorporate E79 as part of the planned “Struma” motorway. To protect the gorge’s unique biodiversity from the deleterious

impacts of roads and comply with EU environmental legislation, this project has consistently been met with opposition both by the scientific community and environmental organisations, which insist that the motorway should be built outside of the gorge.

With this study, our goal was to fill gaps in the knowledge of the local distribution of conservation important species, by analysing locality data for the four terrestrial species of reptiles with high conservation importance (Annex II of Directive 92/43/EEC) occurring within the Kresna Gorge and its surroundings – *Testudo hermanni*, *T. graeca*, *Elaphe quatuorlineata* and *Zamenis situla*, referred from here on as key species. Such analysis will be beneficial for resolving the issue with the route of “Struma” motorway, and will help adhering to national and EU legislation.

Material and methods

The research area included the entire NATURA 2000 “BG0000366 Kresna - Ilindentsi” Special Area of Conservation with a 5 km buffer around it. It covered parts of Struma River Valley, the eastern slopes of Maleshevska Mts, the western and some northern slopes of the Pirin Mts, and some south-western slopes of the Rila Mts. The altitudinal range spanned from 100 to 2800 m a.s.l. (Fig. 1). Kresna Gorge (a major geographic feature in the SAC) runs in a North-South direction and is situated between 41°43'–41°50'N. It represents a deeply incised river valley that gradually widens from north to south (for a detailed physicogeographical characteristic see Hubenov (2001)).

Species' distribution data were collected predominantly by the authors and colleagues, mainly in 2000–2023. In addition, published detailed locality data were also used. Observations were collected either opportunistically or during numerous herpetological studies. The sampling effort was concentrated between March–October (coinciding with peak reptile activity). The sampling effort was uneven (temporally, spatially, number of investigators), and thus, some areas might be understudied.

Species were located by active searches in suitable habitats and microhabitats across the study area (i.e. under stones and logs, in rock crevices), including in the high elevation areas. Accurate geographic coordinates (± 10 m) of each identified individual

were obtained using hand-held GPS units, the field data collection system <https://SmartBirds.org> (comprising a mobile application (SmartBirds Pro) and a web-based interface), or rarely through geographically referenced high-resolution satellite imagery (Google Earth Pro; Google, Mountain View, California, USA).

Data analyses

All observations were collected into a geodatabase. The Kernel Density Estimate (KDE) (Worton 1989) was used to determine the important sites for the four key species. The combined locations of the key species were used to calculate the Utilization Distribution (UD) and “Fixed Kernel” with a bandwidth value determined by the “Plug-in estimator” (Gitzen et al. 2006). The resolution (cell size) of the UD surface was set at 10 m. We calculated 95%, 90%, 50% and 25% isopleths for the key species. The 95% (KDE 0.95) and 90% (KDE 0.9) isopleths represent the sizes of the individual area, and 50% and 25% (KDE 0.5) represent the core areas of activity (Seaman & Powell, 1996; Campioni et al., 2013).

The analyses were conducted using softwares ArcGIS ver. 10.2.1 (ESRI, 2014), its extension Geospatial Modeling Environment (GME) ver. 0.7.3 (Beyer, 2012), R ver. 3.5.1 (R Development Core Team, 2013) and RStudio ver. 1.1.463-2009-2018 (RStudio Team, 2015).

Results

We collected 2834 individual locations of 11 amphibian and 28 reptile species, situated across various parts and elevations throughout most of the research area (Fig. 1). We located the key species in 645 instances: 326 for *Testudo graeca*, 230 for *T. hermanni*, 55 for *Zamenis situla*, and 34 for *Elaphe quatuorlineata* (Supplementary material 01). The located key species were predominantly at elevation between 200 and 300 m a.s.l., and most of them were situated in the Kresna Gorge (Figs 1 and 2; Supplementary material 01). These locations were concentrated mainly between 0 and 1000 m from Struma River, and to the E79 road, respectively, which runs along, and at times in the immediate vicinity to it (e.g. in Kresna Gorge; Figs 2 and 3).

Fig. 1. Localities of amphibians and reptiles within NATURA 2000 “BG0000366 Kresna - Ilindentsi” Special Area of Conservation with a 5 km buffer around it, including Struma River Valley and Kresna Gorge.

The KDE analysis identified three major areas of importance for the four key species (Fig. 4). For two of these areas (situated between Dolna Gradeshnitsa Village and Strumyani Town, and between Strumyani and Sandanski towns, respectively), only the size of

the individual area (KDEs 0.95 and 0.9) could be calculated. The highest concentration of individual locations was within the third area of importance, with its individual area spanning from the northern end of Dolna Gradeshnitsa Village to the northern end

Fig. 2. Vertical distribution of the individual locations of four key species within the NATURA 2000 “BG0000366 Kresna - Ilindentsi” Special Area of Conservation with a 5 km buffer around it: EQ – *Elaphe quatuorlineata* (n = 34); TG – *Testudo graeca* (n = 326); TH – *Testudo hermanni* (n = 230); ZS – *Zamenis situla* (n = 55).

Fig. 3. Distance between the Struma River and the individual locations of four key species within the NATURA 2000 “BG0000366 Kresna - Ilindentsi” Special Area of Conservation with a 5 km buffer around it: EQ – *Elaphe quatuorlineata* (n = 34); TG – *Testudo graeca* (n = 326); TH – *Testudo hermanni* (n = 230); ZS – *Zamenis situla* (n = 55).

of the Kresna Gorge. Within this individual area, two core areas of activity were outlined (KDEs 0.5 and 0.25). The first was situated at the south-eastern end of Kresna Town and was presented only by the KDE 0.5. The second core area (in which the individual locations were with the highest concentration), presented by both KDE 0.5 and KDE 0.25, was situated between the southern and central parts of Kresna Gorge (Fig. 4).

Discussion

Within the research area, the four key species are distributed mainly at lower elevations and usually adhere close to Struma River. Our results highlight the conservation importance of the Kresna Gorge where almost half of the amphibian and two-thirds of the reptile species in Bulgaria can be found (Petrov & Beshkov, 2001; Stojanov et al., 2011). Specifically, Kresna Gorge serves as a hotspot for the four key species in the study area, as well as for many other non-key reptile and amphibian species (Petrov & Beshkov, 2001). Therefore, Kresna Gorge should be considered a high priority area for protection and conservation of the populations of these species. Further-

more, since the distributions of *Z. situla* and *E. quatuorlineata* in Bulgaria are limited mainly and entirely to SW Bulgaria, respectively (Naumov & Tomović, 2007; Stojanov et al., 2011; Beschkov, 2015c, d), Kresna Gorge that marks the regional northern boundary of their ranges, should be considered as an area of critical importance for their conservation on a national instead of local level.

Our study identifies a major threat to the local reptile and amphibian populations, and especially of the four key species – the E79 international road that passes through Kresna Gorge, right next to Struma River. Most observations of the four key species are situated in close proximity to the road. The negative effects of roads on wildlife and especially reptiles have been well-established. Specifically, because reptiles are small and relatively slow-moving, roads are often barriers for their dispersal by leading to direct animal mortality, and disrupt their movements (Ashley & Robinson, 1996; Smith & Dodd, 2003; Meek, 2009; Paterson et al., 2019). In Bulgaria, negative effects on the herpetofauna by roads have been identified as well (Kambourova-Ivanova et al., 2012; Mollov et al., 2013b). The intense traffic on E79, which increases year by year, with hundreds of vehicles daily passing through (National Company “Strategic Infrastructure

Fig. 4. Areas of importance for four key species, outlined by the Kernel Density Estimate (KDE), representing the size of the individual area (KDEs 0.95 and 0.9) and the core area of activity (KDEs 0.5 and 0.25), within NATURA 2000 “BG0000366 Kresna - Ilindentsi” Special Area of Conservation with a 5 km buffer around it. 1 – area of importance between the Kresna Gorge and Dolna Gradeshnitsa Village; 2 – area of importance situated between Dolna Gradeshnitsa Village and Strumyani Town; 3 – area of importance between Strumyani and Sandanski towns.

Projects”, 2014), practically makes this road an almost impossible obstacle for the species’ dispersal, as evident by the numerous individuals that are being killed on it each year (Petrov et al., 2006; authors’ personal observations). Because of the complete lack of de-

tailed population studies on the key species in this area, however, the true effect of this road on their populations remains unknown. It is evident however, that the intensity of this road’s traffic presents a major threat for the populations of the studied species.

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Authors' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Georgi Popgeorgiev: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, software, supervision, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Angel Dyugmedzhiev: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, supervision, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Simeon Lukanov: data curation, investigation, methodology, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Emiliya Vacheva: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Miroslav Slavchev: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Kostadin Andonov: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Vladislav Vergilov: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Deyan Duhalov: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Georgi Krastev: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Andrei Stojanov: data curation, investigation; Nikolay Tzankov: data curation, investigation; Dimitar Plachiyiski: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Yurii V. Kornilev: investigation, methodology, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Borislav Naumov: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, software, supervision, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing.

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Supplementary materials

01

Document title: Coordinates, altitude and source reference of the locations for *Elaphe quatuorlineata*, *Testudo graeca*, *Testudo hermanni* and *Zamenis situla*, used for the analyses in the current study

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